

SEAWATER AGEING OF COMPOSITES FOR OCEAN ENERGY CONVERSION SYTEMS

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SUMMARY

This paper describes a test programme designed to evaluate the durability of composites for ocean energy conversion systems. The critical importance of material selection is illustrated by results from fatigue tests in natural sea water, which show that glass fibre type has a strong influence on lifetime.

Keywords: Marine, Energy, Sea water, Fatigue, Infusion

INTRODUCTION

Recent increases in oil prices have focused attention on alternative sources of energy. Ocean energy is one of the most promising, and the resource can be broadly split into [1-3] ;

- Tides, Waves, Tidal (marine) currents, Temperature gradients, and Salinity gradients.

Several recent evaluations of these resources suggest that they are of the same order as that of the present capacity of electricity generation worldwide [3]. Interest in ocean energy is not new, tidal barrage plants have been operating for many years including the barrage on the Rance estuary, in Brittany, which has been producing electricity since 1966 [4]. What is new is the level of current development and investment, several

demonstration projects in the 0.5 to 1.5 MW range are either being evaluated or will shortly be deployed, particularly wave and tidal current systems.

Many devices have been proposed for wave and tidal energy conversion [1-3] but one feature of all the systems is that long term reliability is essential. Maintenance free operation is a pre-requisite if these systems are to be economically viable. This, together with light weight, is one of the main reasons for considering composites rather than metallic structures for these applications. Fortunately there is extensive experience of composites in marine structures and in this paper a brief overview of this experience will be presented first. Many studies of composites in water are also available and these will be briefly reviewed. Another source of information concerning composites in large structures is wind turbine blades, where cyclic loading has been examined in some detail, and this will then be briefly described. Some short term information has also been gained from prototype ocean energy devices and this will be summarized.

As a result, provided the lessons from this previous in-service experience are assimilated, only the influence of the specific environmental conditions relevant to ocean energy structures requires detailed study today. In the final part of the paper a description of a study specifically aimed at characterizing long term durability of an underwater energy conversion device element, such as a current turbine blade, will be given.

COMPOSITE MARINE STRUCTURES

Glass fibre reinforced polymers have been the preferred material choice for small boat-builders for over 50 years [5,6]. Other applications include high speed ferries, a recent overview [7] provides data for the composites used in marine vessels. Military naval applications have used large quantities of glass reinforced composites since the MCMV (Mine Counter-Measure Vessel) programmes started in the 1960's. Smith has given a detailed overview of the different concepts developed by different navies [8] and some information on large composite submarine structures is also available [9].

The offshore industry has become interested in composite materials in recent years and several large projects have generated both material data (e.g. the Marinotech programme [10]) and prototype experience on structures such as risers [11].

Underwater applications also include oceanographic systems, glass/epoxy has been used in instrumentation housings and benthic landers, two applications developed at Ifremer. The former are generally filament wound cylinders [12] while the latter is a 2 metre high structure designed to remain in deep sea for months or years. Developed in 1997 this is still in service and has been used in campaigns down to more than 4000 meters depth.

Finally, an application very similar to that of wave energy converters is that of navigation buoys, moored at sea and exposed to the environment in very severe conditions. There are over 4000 buoys around the French coast, a recent conference summarized experience in this area where polymer and composite floating buoys are increasingly being used to replace steel [13,14].

Figure 1 : MAP benthic lander

COMPOSITES IN WATER

In parallel with applications in service there have been many laboratory studies of the influence of moisture on composite properties. Early studies focussed on relative humidity but much data was measured [15].

As part of the development of the use of composites for cooling water tubes a large number of durability studies were performed by EDF in collaboration with the authors at Ifremer and the University of Franche Comté [e.g. 16,17]. These studies generated data on composite properties after immersion in water for periods over 10 years, Mechanical properties of aged samples were evaluated periodically and a loss in properties was noted after 2.5 years in water at 60°C. This was attributed to hydrolysis of the epoxy resin, and underlines the importance of resin selection; the anhydride hardener initially selected is not stable over long periods at 60°C. Selection of an alternative hardener solved the problem, though it should be noted that even after 10 years' immersion at 20°C the mechanical properties of the original material were still intact.

FATIGUE LOADING EXPERIENCE (WIND TURBINE STRUCTURES)

There have been many studies of fatigue in composites and a recent book gives a good overview [18]. A major source of data on cyclic loading of composites, both from laboratory tests and in service, is the wind energy industry. Composites are the preferred material for wind turbine blades. Glass reinforced composites have been the first choice since the 1970's, though recently carbon has found some applications as blade lengths extend over 50 meters. Echtermeyer et al. presented results from the EU Joule project [19] in 1996, and more recently the European projects FACT and OPTIMAT have generated large amounts of fatigue data [20].

There is still some discussion over how to model cumulative damage in composites, in particular to take into account the loading history effects related to the chronology of high and low loads [21]. Nevertheless, typical loading spectra have been defined such as the eight proposed in the WISPER (WInd SPECTrum Reference) sequence [22] and these can be used for the evaluation of new designs, both by simulation and to define

appropriate test procedures. In parallel with this approach there has also been considerable interest in reliability based predictions [23].

USE OF COMPOSITES IN PROTOTYPE OCEAN ENERGY STRUCTURES

The amount of information available in the open literature from prototype tests is quite limited as these are generally commercial developments.

Concerning tidal turbines, the Seaflo project, a 300 kW prototype two-blade tidal turbine immersed off the Devon coast in June 2003 [24], used 11 meter diameter composite rotor blades instrumented with strain gauges. The construction involved a central 65mm thick carbon composite spar covered by stiffened glass/epoxy fairings [25]. Also in 2003 a Norwegian tidal power station was installed near Hammerfest, using 10 meter long glass fibre composite blades. In 2008 within the Seagen project a 1.2 MW twin turbine was immersed [26], using a similar design to Seaflo again from Marine Current Turbines. The blades were longer than those trialled in the Seaflo project, each 7.5 meters long. It was reported in July that one of the turbines had shed two blades following a computer incident [27] but the trial is continuing and is being followed closely. Another large scale prototype (500 kW) with 6m composite (glass and carbon) blades was immersed by Tidal Generation Limited in 2009. In the USA, in the RITE project, following development trials with a 3 metre diameter turbine, six turbines were installed in 2007 in New York. These use 4.9 metre diameter turbines each with three composite blades, similar to existing wind turbine designs. Some blade failures were noted and the blades were redesigned.

The first French tidal turbine prototype to be tested at sea was developed within the Sabella project [28]. This is a six-blade turbine made of glass fibre composite fairings on steel spars, which was immersed off the Brittany coast in April 2008. Figure 2a shows the system in service. The blades are composite sandwich structures, including a central metallic spar with glass reinforced composite facings on a foam core, Figure 2b.

Figure 2 : a) Sabella tidal turbine, b) Detail of blade

Other composite tidal turbine blades have been used in the OpenHydro project, and a recent paper described work conducted on composite blades as part of a study for an 11 m diameter blade for a demonstration plant in Japan [29]. In addition to turbine blades,

composites are also of interest for shrouds, mounting frames and other components of these systems.

Composites are also of interest for wave energy devices. For example, Wave Dragon is considering a composite structure for a full-scale, multi-megawatt device (their 20 kW prototype is made of steel), the Pelamis prototype used composites and within FO3, the Norwegian wave power project, a generator is integrated in a floating platform construction which is built in composite.

COLLABORATIVE STUDY ON LONG TERM COMPOSITE DURABILITY

The previous sections have shown that composite materials will be a key element in future ocean energy conversion systems. They show excellent short and long term properties in air and the only area which is not fully understood today is their long term behaviour fully immersed in water. For this reason a study was initiated in 2007 to build on existing knowledge of marine composites and address this point. The partners are 3B and Owens Corning (OCV), major glass fibre suppliers, Hexion the resin producer, Ifremer, and MaHyTec, a company with extensive composite experience. The overall aim of this study is to develop and validate the tools necessary to predict the long term behaviour of composite systems under mechanical loading coupled with immersion in sea water. In the first part of the study it was assumed that the lifetime is governed by the longitudinal properties of the composite, i.e. the properties in the fibre direction as this is the main load-bearing component of the composite. Preliminary blade design is often performed taking a maximum strain in the fibre direction, typically 0.4% for example. The fibre properties are therefore dominant and a critical parameter is the fibre composition. The off-axis properties, strongly dependent on the resin and interface behaviour, will be examined in the second part of the study.

Materials and Manufacturing

Materials for the study have been produced by both hand lay-up and infusion. Hand lay-up has traditionally been used for boat structures, and allows these to be manufactured cheaply. However, the mechanical performance of hand laid-up structures is not optimal, fibre volume contents are typically around 30%. Resin infusion is the preferred route for large industrial structures such as tidal turbines. Fibres are placed in a mould and resin is drawn in by vacuum to impregnate them. Fibre volume fractions around 50-60% can be achieved, resulting in greatly improved mechanical performance compared to hand lay-up. In the first part of the project three types of fibre, the traditional E-glass, and the improved Advantex™ and HiPer-tex™ grades, Table 1.

Table 1 : Glass fibre properties

Fibre type	Density	Tensile modulus GPa	Tensile Strength MPa
E-glass	2.57	78-80	2000-2500
Advantex™	2.62	81-83	2200-2600
High performance glass (HiPer-tex™)	2.55	89-91	3050-3400

These were applied in the form of quasi-unidirectional fabrics, using products used today in wind turbine blade structures. One resin was studied in detail initially, an epoxy

developed for infusion and widely used in the manufacture of wind turbine blades, reference RIM135 from Hexion, Table 2.

Table 2 : Resin properties epoxy RIM 135/137 cure 10h at 70°C

Density	Tensile Modulus GPa	Tensile Strength MPa	Failure strain, %	Tg
1.05-1.15	3.2	75	7	85°C

Within the present project hundreds of specimens were produced for testing. Panels were infused and specimens were prepared using high pressure water jet cutting.

Static properties

Various tests can be performed to characterize the mechanical properties; tensile, compression and flexural tests have been performed within the project. An example showing results from load-unload cycles, which allow damage development to be quantified, applied to the reference E-glass material under tensile and compression loading is shown in Figure 3. Ageing in water has a significant effect on static properties, as shown by the superposed plots in Figure 3, particularly in tension. These results were from tests on samples saturated in sea water at 80°C. Compared to 20°C for example the accelerating factor is around 90x. Thus if it takes 15 days to reach saturation at 80°C it will require around 4 years for the same sample at 20°C. (Note that this is a worst case estimate, it takes no account of the real geometry of a structure, nor surface coatings).

Figure 3 : Damage development in unaged and aged infused E-glass specimens tested under tensile (blue and orange) and compression (green and red) loading-unloading cycles, (one specimen for each loading type)

Creep rupture in sea water

It has been known for many years that the fibre composition is critical to long term integrity of composites mechanically loaded in water, often referred to as stress corrosion resistance [30]. Creep rupture (constant load) tests have been performed in salt water by one of the project partners [31]. The results indicate significantly longer lifetimes for the same resin, (polyester) when Advantex™ fibres replace E-glass. This

underlines the importance of glass selection for long term applications in sea water, but in an application such as a tidal turbine the loads are not constant but cyclic, so this is the loading of interest here.

Diffusion modelling

In order to model water absorption kinetics, weight gain data for the materials have been measured, by gravimetry, on samples placed in the natural sea water ageing facility at Ifremer. This includes tanks with circulating sea water at temperatures from 4 to 80°C, Figure 4a. Figure 4b shows an example of measurements on one material, the epoxy resin used as a matrix in infused composites, indicating how immersion time and water temperature affect weight gain.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4 : Ageing in seawater

a) Natural seawater ageing facility. b) Weight gain data for epoxy infusion resin.

Similar data have been determined for the infused composite, and this allows water ingress to be estimated. It is important to develop a reliable diffusion model as the prediction of property changes depends on accurate knowledge of the spatial and temporal water distribution within the composite structure. The results for the resin used in the composites shown in Figure 3 can be modelled with a Fickian model but this is not the case for all the materials studied here and more complex models are also being studied. Then the damage development under static and cyclic loading conditions in new and aged materials has been studied.

Cyclic loading

Few data are available from fatigue tests on composites in sea water however, though Gao and Weitsman [32] indicated significant reductions in lifetimes for saturated glass fibre reinforced composites compared to dry test results. The principal loading of turbine blades is flexural, but in a complex sandwich structure locally this may result in tension, compression or shear loads dominating. In a four point flexural test all three loadings are present, their contributions depend on the test geometry. The part of the specimen between the upper loading points is in tension on the lower surface and

compression on the upper section, while between the inner and outer loading points interlaminar shear dominates. This specimen is therefore useful to compare damage mechanisms, provided indentation damage can be avoided. A test campaign involving flexural and tensile fatigue loading of samples in natural sea water is currently underway at Ifremer and MaHyTec. Special test fixtures are necessary to avoid corrosion. Figure 5 shows one example of fatigue results for the reference E-glass material and the same resin with High performance glass (HiPerTex™) fibres, tested in the unaged state at 20°C in circulating natural seawater.

Figure 5 : Flexural fatigue tests in seawater at 20°C, R=0.1, 2Hz

Loading case #1 *Loading case #2* *Loading case #3* *Loading case #4* *Loading case #5*
 50% 55% 60% 65% 70%

Figure 6 : Flexural fatigue tests seawater at 20°C, R=0.1, 2Hz for E-glass specimens

These results clearly indicate the importance of the fibre type when long term durability in sea water is required.

In addition to these results for life time, the evolution of a stiffness parameter, defined as the ratio maximum load/maximum displacement of the sample versus the normalized number of cycles N/N_r has been plotted on Figure 6. This shows that there is an initial drop in stiffness, as local indentation occurs, followed by a much more gradual decrease over the majority of the lifetime before a final rapid drop as fibres break in tension.

Coupled analysis of mechanical behaviour and water diffusion

Based on the data from the tests described above the fully coupled behaviour of these materials under cyclic loading in sea water can be modelled, using the Comsol Multiphysics software. The ingress of water into the material as immersion time increases is simulated, and mechanical load is applied simultaneously.

A damage mechanics approach has been used in the past to study the influence of sea water on composite properties [33,34]. A parameter D_{zz} , defined as the % variation in axial modulus, was used to characterize mechanical damage. That work was performed to study the long term behaviour of composite cooling water tubes, and shows how damage, (in the form of resin micro-cracks in this case), can accelerate water entry, and immersion in water can accelerate mechanical damage.

In order to account for the influence of seawater on the fatigue damage mechanisms the S-N plots can be related to water content. This is probably the simplest way to enable wet ageing characteristics to be integrated in the design loop. More complex fatigue damage models could be applied if loading histories are known, and the development of typical loading spectra, similar to those in use for wind turbines, would help both material optimization and structural qualification programmes.

Integration in structural models

Once the material has been characterized the behaviour laws can be introduced into numerical models which enable the long term behaviour of structures such as tidal turbines to be evaluated. Figure 6 shows an example. These blades are complex structures subjected to a complex loading including flexure and torsion. Tests on instrumented tidal turbine blades, both in the wave basin under controlled flow conditions and at sea, are therefore essential to complete the study and allow the models to be validated.

CONCLUSIONS

There is a large amount of data available on the performance of composite materials in a marine environment, and with correct selection of fibres and resins these materials have been shown to perform very well.

There is also a significant amount of data on cyclic loading of large composite structures, from the wind turbine industry, and again their performance is generally excellent.

The area which remains to be checked is the coupling of these two, long term cyclic loading in sea water, and this paper has presented a project currently underway which is examining this aspect in detail.

Improved understanding of the interaction between mechanical damage and seawater should result in improved design to guarantee long term performance of ocean energy conversion structures.

Figure 6. Structural composite tidal turbine blade model.

a) mesh mode, b) load mode, c) deformed mode

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